

WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFICIENCY OF USING DRIP IRRIGATION IN AGRICULTURE

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Annotation

Today, demand for water resources in agriculture is increasing, but a sharp decrease in water and inefficient water loss in irrigation networks are leading to an increase in water supply. In this article, proposals have been developed on how water efficiency can be achieved through the use of innovative water-saving technologies in agriculture and the effectiveness of the use of technologies.

Keywords : water deficit, water management technologies, drip irrigation, cooperation, water organizations, subsidies.

Introduction. The reform of the Republic's agriculture and water economy laid the groundwork for the formation of market factors to encourage fair and efficient management of water distribution. The institutional market conditions created are necessary, but not sufficient, to significantly improve water distribution management. Currently, it is clear that insufficient public participation in the management of Agriculture and water is one of the main limiting factors that prevent the improvement of the efficiency of agricultural production and the quality of water distribution management in the province. In addition, it should be noted that water users ' own interest and initiative should be a decisive factor when applying water-saving technologies. Targeted programs and activities are based on the advanced irrigation technology of governments, network ministries and departments (drip irrigation, irrigation, etc.k.) the work of encouraging use was not effective enough, as can be seen from all past experiences . In this regard, the

process of democratization of management becomes relevant by involving the public in the process of introducing drip irrigation technology through the creation of agricultural cooperatives for the joint use of a new type of Water organizations – drip irrigation technology, i.e. organizations formed by water users (individuals and legal entities).

The president of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the PD-4499 of October 25, 2019 "on measures to expand mechanisms to promote the introduction of water—saving technologies in agriculture".

Methods. In the coverage of the topic, monographic research, comparative comparison, systematic approach and methods of logical thinking were widely used.

Results. Approved forecast indicators for the introduction of water-saving irrigation technologies in 2023

With this decision. To ensure the introduction of water-saving irrigation technologies, water supply is carried out with the help of pumping stations and pumping units, including priority assessment of arable land carried out from irrigation wells and vertical drainage wells:

On January 1, 2020, the cancellation of the procedure for the financial enslavement of rural, agricultural enterprises with the cultivation of cotton raw materials for state

extends on lands with low specificity from the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

On January 1, 2022, it was determined that the procedure for pumping units and irrigation wells for the cultivation of cotton raw materials and bushy grain will be applied to rural, agricultural producers who have introduced only water-saving irrigation technologies in order to increase the value of consumed electricity from the state budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of subsidies.

According to the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 98 dated February 19, 2020 "on measures to cover part of the costs of agricultural producers for the introduction of water-saving irrigation technologies: water-saving technologies subsidies allocated from the state budget for the current made fields are determined by the types of agricultural crops of quantity and through the valuation of coefficients based on the bonitet scores of the land.

The results of the SWOT analysis on the application of drip irrigation technology show that economic entities have a low solvency, system components – a sinking reservoir (a pool with geomembrane), a pump, filters, a transformer, a trunk pipe and the cost of other devices. other elements of the system, the need to provide electricity to the place of application of the technology, as well as the need for a specialist to control the operation of the system are the main reasons that prevent the widespread use of technology

It is worth noting that in developed countries, small agricultural producers also widely use the experience of cooperation in the joint use of techniques. The lack of a complete list of machines designed by individual farmers to hold agrotechnical events is encouraging them to form associations and cooperate.

In foreign practice, machine rings are common-this is a form of combination of farms for the exchange of equipment and the provision of mechanized services. Machine collaborations have become widespread in Germany, Austria, England, Luxembourg, Greece, Belgium and other countries .

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, cooperation is organized and is based on the company form of ownership, voluntary associations (cooperatives) of individuals and legal entities in order to achieve common goals in various areas of economic and social activity.

it makes it possible to develop and establish the principles of democracy in all areas of production and management, the independence of enterprises in solving production and social problems in the country. Cooperation opens up opportunities for effective cooperation, enrichment of public and private property. The wide application of the principles of cooperation allows you to optimally combine large, medium and small enterprises, taking into account the management conditions that contribute to the rational use of Labor and material and Technical Resources, advanced technological processes and the satisfaction of production. the social interests of the members of the partnership.

Taking into account the advantages of applying drip irrigation technology, as well as the cost of installing this system, it is necessary, in our opinion, for small farms to jointly install and jointly install drip irrigation technology.

It should be noted that the cooperative is organized on a voluntary basis at the request or initiative of legal entities. Cooperation subects: cooperative members, Cooperation Council, Executive Group (contract-based employees).

The effectiveness of the collaborative application of drip irrigation technology is as follows:

- centralized coordination and monitoring of the effective and rational use of Water Resources at the level of economic subects located in the same territory;
- rational use of land resources in the construction of ponds, ponds, filters and other elements of drip irrigation technology;
- reduce the cost of purchasing, installing and operating drip irrigation technology by combining the capital of farms to design and purchase structural elements of the drip irrigation system (filler-geomembrane Basin, filter, transformer, pump and

trunk pipe, etc.);

- attracting qualified specialists and experts for the design, installation and maintenance of drip irrigation system;

The use of drip irrigation technology on a cooperative basis reduces costs by 20-25 percent in design, earthworks, procurement, use and maintenance.

Thus, the organization and regulation of the activities of water consumers in the form of a cooperative serves to widely apply drip irrigation technology in the activities of economic subects.

SWOT analysis of the application of drip irrigation technology

From the strong side	Weak side
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -delivery, the right amount of water, fertilizers and microelements from to the root system of the plant; - saving water resources 2-5 times; -intensive crop growth and development; - increase productivity by 30-50% ; - 2-fold reduction in costs for mineral fertilizers; - reduce fuel consumption; - simplifies the fight against weeds and diseases; -increase labor productivity (3-4 operators control sugaring on an area of 100-200); - conducting agrotechnical activities without soundness; - fertile soil layers are not washed; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -high cost of equipment; - limited amount of preferential lending; - collateral (property) is required to obtain a loan; - low quality equipment; - lack of qualified operators; - multi-maintenance coursework and repair costs; - lack of Service exchange centers; - qualified builders are required; - fresh water is needed for sugaring; - requires electricity costs; - inability to use on saline soils; - farmers do not have enough qualifications in the choice of equipment of the dis and construction company;

- removal of erosion in mountainous and mountainous conditions; - lack of drainage flows.	- errors in system design.
Opportunities	Threats
-exempting farms and other organizations from customs duties on importing drip irrigation equipment; -providing preferential loans for up to 3years; -exemption from the single land tax for 5 years.	-changes in legislation (preferential lending and abolition of taxation); - natural disasters (flood flows - water turbidity); - increased price of polyethylene and other components of drip irrigation technology; - increase in the cost of electricity.

Conclusion.

The introduction of innovative water-saving technologies is instrumental in reducing the waste of water resources while requiring high costs. Achieving the efficiency of using water resources only through the use of water-efficient technologies is one solution. However, it is also important to use the tested methods of microbism in managing water resources and organizing the effective use of water.

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